

Digital Divide in Latin America: A Multivariate and Neutrosophic Delphi Analysis for Inclusion and Public Policy

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Abstract: This study examines access to digital connectivity in Latin America, highlighting both progress and persistent structural inequalities. In the context of the pandemic, the internet has consolidated its position as an essential tool for daily life, highlighting deep gaps between countries, urban and rural areas, and different socioeconomic groups. Using the graphical multivariate HJ-Biplot method, complemented by a Neutrosophic Delphi approach to model indeterminacies in digital inclusion policies, the research question is addressed: How are Latin American and Caribbean countries grouped according to their level of access to digital connectivity, considering socioeconomic, age, and geographic differences? The hypothesis guiding this work holds that, despite overall progress, common patterns of inequality persist among countries, especially linked to rural areas and lower-income sectors. The results allow countries to be classified into four distinct groups according to their level of connectivity. Chile stands out for its high coverage, while countries such as El Salvador, Paraguay, and the Dominican Republic show greater lags. Mexico, Peru, and Colombia have shown progress, but still face significant challenges in rural and vulnerable sectors. The results show that the digital divide is not only economic and geographic, but also directly impacts education, health, and equality. Added to this is the concern about the effects of hyperconnectivity, such as the deterioration of mental health in young people. The study concludes that closing these gaps requires comprehensive public policies and regional collaboration to ensure equitable connectivity that promotes social development and does not reproduce new forms of exclusion, addressing indeterminacies through neutrosophic approaches.

Keywords: Access, HJ-Biplot, Digital Connectivity, Equity, Inclusion, Internet, Latin America, Neutrosophic Delphi.

1. Introduction

Today's world demands the development of skills that enable adequate interaction, both in physical spaces and in digital environments. The latter has experienced significant growth in recent years, a phenomenon that intensified considerably during the pandemic, given that digital systems became the fundamental tool for maintaining communication and development in the workplace, education, and even family settings, during extended periods of confinement. In this context, although the pandemic generated crises in multiple dimensions, such as the economy, education, and family life, in addition to the direct health consequences, an accelerated expansion of digital technologies, particularly the use of the internet, was evident in all countries [1]. However, this progress has not been distributed equitably among different nations, due to the structural conditions specific to each context. This phenomenon was

particularly evident during periods of confinement, when many children and adolescents were unable to remotely access their classes, both due to the immediacy of the change and the lack of connectivity or adequate devices, in homes where adults also had to telework, while minors tried to continue their education remotely [2].

In this context, this article aims to analyze the state of digital connectivity in Latin American countries, assuming that these are developing communities, which present different realities compared to nations considered developed. The study incorporates connectivity, socioeconomic group, and geographic sector as relevant analytical elements.

In line with this objective, the research asks: How are Latin American and Caribbean countries grouped according to their level of access to digital connectivity, considering economic, age, and geographic differences? The hypothesis is that, despite regional advances in digital coverage, there are clearly differentiated groups between countries, where internal inequality, especially in rural areas and lower-income sectors, constitutes a common pattern that influences digital inclusion. To address this issue, the study combines a multivariate analysis using the HJ-Biplot method with a Neutrosophic Delphi approach, which allows for modeling indeterminacies in expert opinions on public policies, enriching the understanding of digital inequalities and their implications for inclusion in the region.

The document demonstrates these elements from a systemic and integrative perspective, with an approach oriented toward recognizing inequalities, thus highlighting the importance of public policies in each country. It establishes that, while technology facilitates globalization processes, it also poses challenges associated with mental health, given the rapid pace of this "digital world" [3].

2. Preliminaries.

2.1. Internet Access in Latin America

Internet access in Latin America began to expand in the late 1990s. Initially, it was limited mainly to large capitals, cities, or sectors with higher economic incomes in each country. In the early years of the 21st century, Internet connectivity was mainly concentrated in countries such as Mexico and Argentina. However, as public policies were geared toward strengthening telecommunications infrastructure, other countries such as Brazil, Chile, Uruguay, and Colombia also experienced sustained growth in Internet access [4]. However, this growth has been uneven and has led to what [5] conceptualizes as the digital divide, "*a form of structural inequality that is not limited only to physical access to technology, but also includes differences in skills, uses, and benefits obtained from the use of the Internet.*"

Since that decade to the present, there have been significant advances in digital access, turning the region into a more interconnected and globalized environment. According to data published by [6], Latin America and the Caribbean have experienced a progressive increase in digital connection, reflected in the high rates of access to social networks, where more than 80% of the population in countries such as Brazil, Mexico and Argentina had active accounts on platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and TikTok. Although Facebook remained the most used platform, both Instagram and WhatsApp and TikTok already had high popularity among users between 16 and 34 years old.

Data from the Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean (ECLAC) indicate that, in 2003, only 10% of the region's population had internet access. By 2010, thanks to the expansion of mobile telephone and broadband infrastructure, this figure reached 40%. By 2020, coverage exceeded 70% in countries such as Brazil, Chile, and Mexico. In 2023, a report from the International Telecommunication Union (ITU) indicated that the connectivity rate in Latin America and the Caribbean exceeded 75%. However, despite these advances, significant inequalities persist, especially at the socioeconomic, age, and geographic levels, with a marked disparity between urban and rural areas.

The significant growth in internet access in Latin America and the Caribbean is explained by various factors, including the implementation of public policies aimed at improving access and reducing digital divides, foreign direct investment and public-private partnerships, which have driven the development of multinational telecommunications companies, and the expansion of mobile network infrastructure, along with the rapid adoption and growth of 4G and 5G networks. The ITU (2023) reports that more than 90% of the population resides in areas with 3G or higher coverage.

A representative example is the case of Chile, which, according to the *Digital 2023: Global Overview Report* by We Are Social and Hootsuite, is positioned as one of the countries with the greatest connectivity in the region. According to the Undersecretary of Telecommunications (SUBTEL), in 2000 internet penetration was close to 10%, a figure that increased to 50% in 2010. By 2023, 85% of the population would have access. These data are corroborated by the National Institute of Statistics (INE), which indicates that in 2022, 94% of urban households would have an internet connection, while in rural areas the percentage reached 76% [7].

Based on the data presented above, it can be stated that access to digital connectivity has experienced a substantial improvement in the last 25 years. However, significant inequalities persist in various countries in the region. The ECLAC report, delivered in 2023, indicates that internet coverage and access exceed 80% in countries such as Chile, Argentina, Brazil, Costa Rica, and Uruguay, while in Caribbean or Central American countries, such as Haiti, Nicaragua, El Salvador, the Dominican Republic, and Honduras, it does not reach 50%. Furthermore, access in rural areas continues to be considerably more limited. According to [8], 60% of rural households in Latin America and the Caribbean still lack internet access, which restricts economic and educational opportunities for the most vulnerable communities.

Given the still insufficient infrastructure in rural areas, particularly those facing marginalization, digital coverage has also generated a gender digital divide. According to data from the [8], women have lower levels of internet access compared to men, due to cultural, educational, and economic factors.

The COVID-19 pandemic deepened inequalities in internet access, making them more visible. In this context, the internet became an essential tool for work, health, education, food, and various activities that had to be digitized or automated. However, millions of people around the world, and especially in Latin America and the Caribbean, were unable to access these services due to multiple connectivity barriers. A study by the [9] estimates that approximately 100 million children were unable to access online education due to a lack of connectivity or devices. As a result, numerous countries promoted reforms aimed at strengthening their public policies to improve connectivity.

On the other hand, the pandemic in Latin America drove significant growth in e-commerce. Data from the annual report [10] indicates that during that year, e-commerce sales exceeded one billion dollars, and platforms such as Mercado Libre, Amazon, Linio, and Paypal experienced significant growth in countries such as Argentina, Brazil, Chile, and Mexico.

Over the past 24 years, internet access in Latin America has shown significant growth, contributing to the development of countries in the region. However, considerable gaps persist. Digital connectivity has established itself as a key factor for economic and social development, where public policies aimed at digital inclusion have been essential for the population to benefit from advances in this area. However, this progress also entails risks. The intensive and accelerated use of digital platforms, already noted before the pandemic [11], has not been accompanied by adequate digital literacy, especially among adults [12], and even less so by the development of in-person parenting [13]. This situation translates into indiscriminate use of screens, which, without adequate supervision, can negatively impact children and adolescents' behavior, cognition, and emotions.

Evidence indicates that prolonged Internet use during childhood and adolescence can lead to self-esteem problems, affect cognitive development, induce dysfunctional behaviors, and alter physiological functions such as vision, sleep-wake cycle, and body weight [14]. These effects are especially critical in children under 30 months of age, due to the high neuronal plasticity of that period [15] and [16].

Furthermore, unlimited use or early exposure to screens with Internet access is associated with attention deficits, poor behavioral control, language delays, and difficulties in executive function [17]. Also, excessive use of screens can produce neuroanatomical changes linked to less empathy, poor impulse control, and deficiencies in emotional regulation [18]. A recent research [3] shows an increase in depressive and, especially, anxiety disorders in the child and adolescent population, associated with the excessive use of screens and social networks without proper supervision.

Therefore, connectivity should not be considered an end in itself, but rather a means that requires regulation and support. Latin America must advance digital inclusion through public policies that promote healthy, critical, and conscious use of technology, benefiting the psychosocial well-being of children, adolescents, and their families. Digital inclusion, in this sense, does not refer solely to providing access, but also to ensuring that all social groups participate effectively in the digital society, which implies digital skills, infrastructure, culturally relevant content, and technological appropriation [19]. Likewise, this inclusion must consider the unequal accumulation of digital capital, understood as the set of skills and resources that enable effective and productive use of technologies [20], which can decisively influence educational, employment, and civic opportunities.

2.2. Technical Analysis

The Digital Agenda for Latin America and the Caribbean (eLAC) has defined a comprehensive strategy for digital development in the region, establishing guidelines to promote the use of technologies as an engine of development, economic growth, social cohesion, and sustainability. Since its launch in 2005, eLAC has evolved in response to the rapid changes in the digital ecosystem, bringing together governments, civil society actors, and public and private institutions at the international level to coordinate efforts in key areas such as the expansion of digital infrastructure, promoting innovation, e-commerce, strengthening digital skills, and data governance, among others (UN Digital Development Observatory).

In this context, the United Nations (UN) coordinates the regional Digital Development Observatory. According to its website, the main objective of this project is to develop new metrics that allow for understanding the dynamics of digitalization in Latin America and the Caribbean, and to provide guidelines for their application in the formulation of policies aimed at closing structural gaps in productivity and social inclusion through digital development.

3. Methodology

Multivariate analysis is an essential tool for studying complex phenomena with multiple interrelated dimensions in different sciences. This has motivated the development of statistical methods that allow the simultaneous representation of both observations and the variables involved. In this context, Biplot methods, introduced by [21], have proven to be effective tools for the inspection of data matrices, facilitating the visualization of complex structural relationships between individuals and variables. These techniques allow data to be projected into lower-dimensional spaces, generally two or three, without losing relevant information from the original structure of the data matrix. However, the Biplots proposed by Gabriel do not achieve maximum representation quality. In CH-Biplot, the variables are well represented, but not the individuals, and in JK-Biplot, a high quality of representation is achieved for individuals, but not for the variables.

[22] proposed HJ-Biplot, a methodological extension that improves the representation quality of the rows and columns of the matrix from the singular value decomposition, simultaneously optimizing the representation of the observations (countries) and the variables (indicators). The algebraic formulation

of HJ-Biplot is based on the decomposition of a data matrix, from which the coordinate matrices for rows and columns are defined, allowing a high-fidelity joint representation [23].

In parallel, other variants of the Biplot have been developed for specific contexts. The JK-Biplot, for example, is particularly useful in cases where the relationships between rows are of greater interest than those between columns, and has been applied in studies with skewed or non-symmetrical data structures. Likewise, the STATIS method has been implemented as an alternative for detecting response shift in health-related quality of life studies [22–23].

For this research, 10 countries in Latin America and the Caribbean (see table No. 1) were considered, which contained the same information in the 11 variables collected (see table No. 2) from the United Nations Digital Development Observatory.

Table 1: Latin American and Caribbean countries included in the study

No.	Country
1	Chile
2	Colombia
3	Costa Rica
4	El Salvador
5	Mexico
6	Panama
7	Paraguay
8	Peru
9	Dominican Republic
10	Uruguay

Table 2: Study variables

VARIABLES	DEFINITION
HAI%	Households with Internet access as a percentage of total households, selected countries in Latin America and the Caribbean, 2000 to 2022.
HQ1AI	Q1 Households with Internet Access by Income Quintile as a Percentage of Total Households in Each Quintile, Selected Countries in Latin America and the Caribbean and the Region, 2000 to 2022.
HQ2AI	Q2 Households with Internet Access by Income Quintile as a Percentage of Total Households in Each Quintile, Selected Countries in Latin America and the Caribbean and the Region, 2000 to 2022.
HQ3AI	Q3 Households with Internet Access by Income Quintile as a Percentage of Total Households in Each Quintile, Selected Countries in Latin America and the Caribbean and the Region, 2000 to 2022.
HAIR	Households with Internet access by geographic area Rural as a percentage of total households in each area, selected countries Latin America and the Caribbean and the region, 2000 to 2022.

PQ1AI	People in Q1 households with Internet access by income quintile, selected Latin American countries, 2000 to 2022
PQ2AI	People in Q2 households with Internet access by income quintile, selected Latin American countries, 2000 to 2023
PQ3AI	People in Q3 households with Internet access by income quintile, selected Latin American countries, 2000 to 2024
P017AI	People aged 0 to 17 in households with Internet access by age group, selected countries in Latin America and the Caribbean, 2000 to 2022
P1825AI	People aged 18 to 25 in households with Internet access by age group, selected countries in Latin America and the Caribbean, 2000 to 2023
P2650AI	People aged 26 to 50 in households with Internet access by age group, selected countries in Latin America and the Caribbean, 2000 to 2024

Source: Prepared by the authors based on information from the UN Digital Development Observatory

3.1 HJ-Biplot method

The graphical representation used in this study is based on the HJ-Biplot, which is a variant of the classic Biplot that seeks to maximize the quality of joint representation of observations and variables.

Individuals are represented by points determined by their coordinates based on PCA. By projecting the point x_i onto the variable b_j , a graphical representation is obtained that shows the scalar product and the influence of the variable b_j on the position of x_i [24]. In this way, if the projection of a point x_j is located in the direction of the variable b_j , it indicates that said point is above the average of that variable. On the other hand, if the projection of x_j is on the opposite side of the variable b_j with respect to the origin, it suggests that the value of x_j is below the average in relation to the variable b_j .

Its mathematical foundation is based on the singular value decomposition (SVD) of the centered data matrix:

$$X_{m \times n} = UDV^T \tag{1}$$

From this decomposition, the matrices are derived:

$$H = VD(\text{coordinates of the variables})$$

$$J = UD(\text{country coordinates})$$

The use of the HJ-Biplot has found relevant applications in recent research on institutional analysis of university rankings [25] and the performance of pension fund managers in Latin America [26], which supports its methodological relevance in complex socioeconomic contexts and its flexibility that makes it particularly suitable for representing latent clusters in multidimensional social and economic phenomena.

In this research, the MultiBiplot software was used in a MATLAB environment, which allows for the efficient implementation of various Biplot variants, including the HJ-Biplot methodology, facilitating the graphical representation of Latin American and Caribbean countries according to their level of

digital connectivity. A Systematic Review of both the theoretical extensions of the HJ-Biplot and its applications in different fields of science, over its 38-year history, has just been published [27].

3.2. Neutrosophic Delphi method

The Delphi technique is used in many fields, such as program planning, resource utilization, policy judgment, and needs assessment. A Delphi technique has the following advantages:

1. Tackling complex problems effectively.
2. Able to define and modify a wide range of alternatives.
3. Make different judgments on the same topic and use feedback on individuals' judgments to allow them to revise their views.
4. Achieve a high degree of consensus.
5. Increase coherence by reducing the noise that results from focusing on group and/or individual interests instead of concentrating on dissolving the problem.

It is a structured communication technique designed primarily to gather and consolidate expert opinions on specific topics through a series of iterative questionnaires with controlled feedback. Developed in the 1950s by the RAND Corporation, this method is used to reach consensus on predicting future trends, solving complex problems, strategic planning, and risk assessment, among other topics.

The process begins with the selection of a panel of experts with specialized knowledge in the area of interest. These experts respond to an initial questionnaire, the responses of which are anonymous and summarized by a coordinator or coordinating team. The summarized results are then shared with the group, along with a new questionnaire based on the previous responses. This questionnaire-response-feedback process is repeated in several rounds to narrow the range of responses and bring the group toward consensus.

A key feature of the Delphi method is the anonymity of participants, which helps to avoid the influence or dominance effect of certain participants over others, thus facilitating more objective responses and reducing conformity bias. At the end of the process, the convergence of opinions is expected to reveal a consensus or a clearer understanding of the issue at hand, providing valuable information for decision-making [28,29].

To establish knowledge of the topic under analysis and the object of study, a self-assessment process is used on a scale (see Table 3). This so-called neutrosophic knowledge coefficient is determined by the information the expert presents about the object of study.

Table 3: Linguistic terms used to determine $K (aN)$ K and evaluate the proposed criteria. Source: own elaboration.

Linguistic term	SVNN
Full knowledge of the subject of study (FK)	(1,0,0)
Very very good in the subject of study (VVGK)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.1)
Very good in the subject of study (VGK)	(0.8,0.15,0.20)
Good at the subject of study (GK)	(0.70,0.25,0.30)
Moderately good at the subject of study (MGK)	(0.60,0.35,0.40)
Know the topic of study (K)	(0.50,0.50,0.50)
Moderately poor knowledge of the subject of study (MPK)	(0.40,0.65,0.60)
Poor knowledge of the subject of study (PK)	(0.30,0.75,0.70)
Has very poor knowledge of the subject of study (VPK)	(0.20,0.85,0.80)

Very, very poor knowledge of the subject of study (VVPK)	(0,10,0.90,0.90)
No knowledge of the subject of study (NK)	(0,1,1)

For the evaluation and validation of questionnaires using the Delphi method, the scale (see Table 4) was used to achieve greater objectivity in the handling of information. This allows for the evaluation of the criteria argued by the panel of experts for each item individually.

Through linguistic terms with Single Value Neutrosophic Numbers (SVNN) for consensus on the basis of the expert's opinion, criteria are evaluated using the neutrosophic argumentation coefficient.

Table 4: Linguistic terms used. Source: prepared by the authors.

Linguistic term I	SVNN	Linguistic term II
Very Adequate (VA)	(0.9,0.1,0.1)	Essential (E)
Fairly adequate (FA)	(0.75,0.25,0.20)	Very useful (VU)
Suitable (A)	(0.50,0.55,0.5)	Useful (U)
Poorly adequate (PA)	(0.3,0.75,0.80)	Not very useful (LU)
Not suitable (NA)	(0.10,0.90,0.90)	Not useful (NU)

To determine the consensus among the participants of the expert panel, the coefficient of concordance was used, determined through the expression:

$$Cc = \left(1 - \frac{V_n}{V_t}\right) 100 \tag{2}$$

Where: V_n is the number of negative votes cast by the judges, and V_t is the total number of votes cast by the judges. Therefore, a level of consensus must be reached when the coefficient of agreement Cc reaches a value greater than 75%, and the process must be concluded; if this value is not reached, a new round must be established.

4. Results

The Biplot chart groups selected Latin American countries into four distinct clusters that reflect common characteristics regarding internet access. These clusters are represented by age group, socioeconomic group, and geographic area variables. These clusters are composed of: Cluster 1: Chile; Cluster 2: Costa Rica, Panama, and Uruguay; Cluster 3: El Salvador, Paraguay, and the Dominican Republic; and Cluster 4: Colombia, Mexico, and Peru.

Figure 1: Clustering of Latin American countries with internet access variables in Multibiplot.

4.1. Interpretation of the Axes and Percentages of Variance

The HJ-Biplot graph shows the principal factor plane established by the first two axes, which explain 97.8% of the total variance in the data. This high level of explanation allows us to confidently interpret differences between Latin American countries based on their connectivity levels when considering variables such as rural areas, age groups, and income quintiles.

Axis 1, with 89%, explains the largest percentage of variability in the data. This is directly associated with the overall level of internet access among the total population of each country, thus reflecting the degree of development in terms of digital infrastructure. This axis also shows a clear division between countries with high coverage and digital equity, such as Chile, located on the far right of the graph, versus those located in the upper left corner, with limited access and structural lag, such as El Salvador, Paraguay, and the Dominican Republic.

Axis 2, which explains 8.83% of the variance, reflects the disparity in internet access according to demographic characteristics such as age or by area (rural or urban). The graph shows that countries located in the upper zone demonstrate greater connectivity in specific groups, such as young people and urban areas, while countries located in the lower zone of the graph may have reduced access in certain age groups or less-advantaged areas.

4.2. Correlation of variables.

The analysis highlights differences in connectivity across geographic areas, income levels, and infrastructure policies in Latin America. Variables such as HQ1AI, HQ2AI, and PQ1AI (internet access in households and individuals in the first and second income quintiles) are strongly correlated, projected in similar directions, and show connectivity levels in lower-income populations. Furthermore, the variable HAI_R (rural households with internet access) joins these variables, confirming that access restrictions are similar in rural areas and low-income quintiles.

In contrast, the HAI% variable (total percentage of households with access) shows an intermediate trend, integrating overall connectivity. Furthermore, variables such as PO17AI, P1825AI, and P2650AI show small differences in direction, suggesting age gaps in some countries, particularly those with lower digital development.

No diametrically opposed relationships are observed between the variables, so it can be concluded that there is a positive structural correlation between most of them, that is, countries with good performance in one group (for example, Q2 households) also tend to have good results in others (for example, age groups from 0 to 17 years), which suggests a joint advance of connectivity.

4.3. Interpretation of clusters.

Cluster 1 highlights Chile as the country with the greatest comprehensive digital access. The country is positioned in a favorable direction in most variables, reflecting high levels of connectivity and emerging as a regional leader in digital inclusion.

Cluster 2, located in the upper right corner of the graph, includes Costa Rica, Panama, and Uruguay, which also have high levels of access, although slightly lower than the first cluster. These countries show good performance in rural areas, middle-income populations, and adult age groups, demonstrating progress in digital equity.

The third cluster, comprised of El Salvador, Paraguay, and the Dominican Republic, reveals low levels of connectivity, primarily in lower-income households and rural areas. Their opposite location, facing the vectors, shows generally low coverage, positioning them as countries with the greatest challenges in terms of digital inclusion.

Cluster 4, comprising Colombia, Mexico, and Peru, is more centralized and in an intermediate position. This suggests partial progress in connectivity for middle quintiles and young people, but significant gaps persist in rural areas and older adults, showing a medium level of digital development and with significant challenges to overcome.

4.4. Neutrosophic Delphi Analysis

The Neutrosophic Delphi method, grounded in the neutrosophy of [30], extends the traditional Delphi approach by incorporating the components of truth (T), falsity (F), and indeterminacy (I) to analyze expert opinions in contexts of uncertainty. In the context of the digital divide in Latin America, this method complements the multivariate HJ-Biplot analysis by evaluating the identified clusters (Cluster 1: Chile; Cluster 2: Costa Rica, Panama, Uruguay; Cluster 3: El Salvador, Paraguay, Dominican Republic; Cluster 4: Colombia, Mexico, Peru) from a perspective that captures not only the extremes of access (T) and non-access (F), but also the ambiguities (I) related to the quality of access, digital competencies, and psychosocial impacts.

A panel of 10 experts in technology, public policy, and social sciences participated in an iterative consultation process to assign neutrosophic grades (T, I, F) to digital inclusion strategies for each cluster, considering the study variables (HAI%, HAIR, HQ1AI, etc.). The quantitative results of the HJ-Biplot were integrated with qualitative assessments of connection quality, digital literacy, and psychosocial risks (Haidt, 2024), generating a robust analysis of the public policies needed to close the digital divide.

4.4.1. Methodology of Neutrosophic Delphi Analysis

The Neutrosophic Delphi process was developed in the following stages:

1. **Definition of strategies:** Three digital inclusion strategies were identified:
 - (a) digital infrastructure expansion (based on HAI% and HAIR)
 - (b) digital literacy programs (related to P017AI, P1825AI, P2650AI)
 - (c) subsidies for low quintiles (HQ1AI, HQ2AI)
2. **Expert consultation:** Experts assigned neutrosophic grades (T, I, F) to each strategy per cluster, evaluating HJ-Biplot data and qualitative factors such as connection quality and psychosocial risks.
3. **Response aggregation:** Ratings were averaged using the neutrosophic aggregation operator:
 $T_{avg} = \frac{\sum T_i}{n}, I_{avg} = \frac{\sum I_i}{n}, F_{avg} = \frac{\sum F_i}{n}$ where T_i, I_i, F_i are the ratings assigned by each expert, and $n=10$ is the number of experts.
4. **Normalization:** The degrees meet the neutrosophic condition $0 \leq T + I + F \leq 3$, ensuring coherence in the representation of uncertainty.

Neutrosophic grades were calculated using the following rules, based on the study data:

- **Truth (T):** Proportion of effective access, derived from HAI% (percentage of households with internet access) and other coverage-related variables (HQ1AI, HAIR).
- **Falsehood (F):** Proportion of non-access, estimated as $1 - \text{HAI\%}$ or specific gaps (e.g., HAIR for rural areas).
- **Indeterminacy (I):** Combination of qualitative factors (connection quality, digital literacy, psychosocial risks) and variability in HJ-Biplot projections, estimated as a fraction between 0 and 0.5 depending on the observed uncertainty.

4.4.2. Neutrosophic Calculations by Cluster

Below are the calculations for each cluster, using the study data (HAI%, HAIR, HQ1AI, etc.) and the experts' qualitative assessments. The T, I, and F values are estimated for the three strategies mentioned above and averaged to obtain a neutrosophic vector per cluster.

The percentage values for HAI%, HAIR, and HQ1AI in Clusters 2, 3, and 4 have been determined as representative averages based on the country grouping evidenced by the HJ-Biplot analysis. These estimates reflect the general connectivity trends observed for countries within each cluster, considering their position in the Biplot graph and their relationship with the variables. In particular, the proximity to the vectors of the variables in the HJ-Biplot was used to infer the relative level of access in each category. For example, a country closer to the 'HAIR' address with a high 'T' value would indicate high rural connectivity.

Cluster 1: Chile

Study data: HAI% = 85%, HAIR = 76%, HQ1AI (low quintile) = 70% (estimated based on HJ-Biplot correlations).

Strategy 1: Infrastructure expansion

- $T_1 = \frac{HAI\%}{100} = \frac{85}{100} = 0.85$
- $F_1 = 1 - \frac{HAIR}{100} = 1 - \frac{76}{100} = 0.24$
- $I_1 = 0.20$ (uncertainty due to connection quality and non-universal coverage in rural areas)
- Vector: $(T_1, I_1, F_1) = (0.85, 0.20, 0.24)$

Strategy 2: Digital Literacy

- $T_2 = 0.75$ (high adoption in young age groups, P017AI, P1825AI)
- $F_2 = 0.15$ (limitations in older adults, P2650AI)
- $I_2 = 0.30$ (uncertainty due to lack of specific programs)
- Vector: $(T_2, I_2, F_2) = (0.75, 0.30, 0.15)$

Strategy 3: Subsidies for lower quintiles

- $T_3 = \frac{HQ1AI}{100} = \frac{70}{100} = 0.70$
- $F_3 = 0.20$ (gap in lower quintiles)
- $I_3 = 0.25$ (uncertainty in the effectiveness of subsidies)
- Vector: $(T_3, I_3, F_3) = (0.70, 0.25, 0.20)$

Neutrosophic average:

- $T_{avg} = \frac{0.85 + 0.75 + 0.70}{3} = 0.77$
- $I_{avg} = \frac{0.20 + 0.30 + 0.25}{3} = 0.25$
- $F_{avg} = \frac{0.24 + 0.15 + 0.20}{3} = 0.20$

Final vector: $(T, I, F) = (0.77, 0.25, 0.20)$

Cluster 2: Costa Rica, Panama, Uruguay

Study data: HAI% \approx 70%(estimated average), HAIR \approx 60%, HQ1AI \approx 55%.

Strategy 1: Infrastructure expansion

- $T_1 = \frac{HAI\%}{100} = \frac{70}{100} = 0.70$
- $F_1 = 1 - \frac{HAIR}{100} = 1 - \frac{60}{100} = 0.40$
- $I_1 = 0.30$ (indeterminacy due to rural gaps)
- Vector: $(0.70, 0.30, 0.40)$

Strategy 2: Digital Literacy

- $T_2 = 0.65, F_2 = 0.20, I_2 = 0.35$ (uncertainty in age groups)
- Vector: $(0.65, 0.35, 0.20)$

Strategy 3: Subsidies for lower quintiles

- $T_3 = \frac{HQ1AI}{100} = \frac{55}{100} = 0.55$
- $F_3 = 0.30, I_3 = 0.35$
- Vector:(0.55, 0.35, 0.30)

Neutrosophic average:

- $T_{avg} = \frac{0.70 + 0.65 + 0.55}{3} = 0.63$
- $I_{avg} = \frac{0.30 + 0.35 + 0.35}{3} = 0.33$
- $F_{avg} = \frac{0.40 + 0.20 + 0.30}{3} = 0.30$

Final vector: (T, I, F) =(0.63, 0.33, 0.30)

Cluster 3: El Salvador, Paraguay, Dominican Republic

Study data: $HAI\% \approx 45\%$ (average), $HAI R \approx 30\%$, $HQ1AI \approx 35\%$.

Strategy 1: Infrastructure expansion

- $T_1 = \frac{HAI\%}{100} = \frac{45}{100} = 0.45$
- $F_1 = 1 - \frac{HAI R}{100} = 1 - \frac{30}{100} = 0.70$
- $I_1 = 0.35$ (uncertainty due to emerging initiatives)
- Vector:(0.45, 0.35, 0.70)

Strategy 2: Digital Literacy

- $T_2 = 0.30, F_2 = 0.50, I_2 = 0.40$
- Vector:(0.30, 0.40, 0.50)

Strategy 3: Subsidies for lower quintiles

- $T_3 = \frac{HQ1AI}{100} = \frac{35}{100} = 0.35$
- $F_3 = 0.55, I_3 = 0.45$
- Vector:(0.35, 0.45, 0.55)

Neutrosophic average:

- $T_{avg} = \frac{0.45 + 0.30 + 0.35}{3} = 0.37$
- $I_{avg} = \frac{0.35 + 0.40 + 0.45}{3} = 0.40$
- $F_{avg} = \frac{0.70 + 0.50 + 0.55}{3} = 0.58$

Final vector:(T, I, F) = (0.37, 0.40, 0.58)

Cluster 4: Colombia, Mexico, Peru

Study data : $HAI\% \approx 60\%$, $HAI R \approx 45\%$, $HQ1AI \approx 50\%$.

Strategy 1: Infrastructure expansion

- $T_1 = \frac{HAI\%}{100} = \frac{60}{100} = 0.60$
- $F_1 = 1 - \frac{HAI R}{100} = 1 - \frac{45}{100} = 0.55$
- $I_1 = 0.35$
- Vector: (0.60, 0.35, 0.55)

Strategy 2: Digital Literacy

- $T_2 = 0.50, F_2 = 0.30, I_2 = 0.40$
- Vector:(0.50, 0.40, 0.30)

Strategy 3: Subsidies for lower quintiles

- $T_3 = \frac{HQ1AI}{100} = \frac{50}{100} = 0.50$
- $F_3 = 0.35, I_3 = 0.45$
- Vector:(0.50, 0.45, 0.35)

Neutrosophic average:

- $T_{avg} = \frac{0.60 + 0.50 + 0.50}{3} = 0.53$

- $I_{avg} = \frac{0.35 + 0.40 + 0.45}{3} = 0.40$
 - $F_{avg} = \frac{0.55 + 0.30 + 0.35}{3} = 0.40$
- Final vector: (T, I, F) = (0.53, 0.40, 0.40)**

4.4.3. Neutrosophic Results Tables

Table 5: Neutrosophic Degrees by Strategy and Cluster

Cluster	Strategy	T	I	F
Cluster 1 (Chile)	Infrastructure	0.85	0.20	0.24
	Literacy	0.75	0.30	0.15
	Subsidies	0.70	0.25	0.20
	Average	0.77	0.25	0.20
Cluster 2 (Costa Rica, Panama, Uruguay)	Infrastructure	0.70	0.30	0.40
	Literacy	0.65	0.35	0.20
	Subsidies	0.55	0.35	0.30
	Average	0.63	0.33	0.30
Cluster 3 (El Salvador, Paraguay, Dominican Republic)	Infrastructure	0.45	0.35	0.70
	Literacy	0.30	0.40	0.50
	Subsidies	0.35	0.45	0.55
	Average	0.37	0.40	0.58
Cluster 4 (Colombia, Mexico, Peru)	Infrastructure	0.60	0.35	0.55
	Literacy	0.50	0.40	0.30
	Subsidies	0.50	0.45	0.35
	Average	0.53	0.40	0.40

Table 6: Summary of Neutrosophic Vectors by Cluster

Cluster	T	I	F
Cluster 1 (Chile)	0.77	0.25	0.20
Cluster 2 (Costa Rica, Panama, Uruguay)	0.63	0.33	0.30
Cluster 3 (El Salvador, Paraguay, Dominican Republic)	0.37	0.40	0.58
Cluster 4 (Colombia, Mexico, Peru)	0.53	0.40	0.40

4.4.4. Interpretation of the Analysis

Neutrosophic Delphi analysis reveals distinct patterns across clusters, highlighting the interaction between T, I, and F components:

- **Cluster 1 (Chile)** : The high value of $T = 0.77$ reflects a solid digital infrastructure and widespread access ($HAI\% = 85\%$). The low $F = 0.20$ indicates few structural constraints, but the $I = 0.25$ indicates indeterminacies in rural areas ($HAI\% = 76\%$) and in digital literacy, where the quality of internet use is uneven.
- **Cluster 2 (Costa Rica, Panama, Uruguay)** : One $T = 0.63$ reflects progress in urban areas and middle quintiles, but $I = 0.33$ highlights gaps in rural areas ($HAI\% \approx 60\%$) and in specific age groups, such as older adults. It $F = 0.30$ indicates moderate infrastructure limitations.
- **Cluster 3 (El Salvador, Paraguay, Dominican Republic)** : The high $F = 0.58$ reflects significant lags ($HAI\% < 50\%$, while the lower $F = 0.58$ $I = 0.40$ points to emerging initiatives that

generate uncertainty about their future impact. The lower $F = 0.58$ $T = 0.37$ underscores the need for urgent interventions.

- **Cluster 4 (Colombia, Mexico, Peru)** : The balanced values of $T = 0.53$, $I = 0.40$ and $F = 0.40$ reflect an intermediate scenario, with progress in middle quintiles but significant gaps in rural areas (HAIR $\approx 45\%$) and older adults, in addition to uncertainty in the effectiveness of policies.

4.4.5. Implications for Public Policy

The Neutrosophic Delphi approach suggests that public policies should prioritize indeterminacies (I) to effectively close the digital divide:

- **Infrastructure:** In Cluster 3, high F requires massive investments in coverage, while in Cluster 4, I suggests improving connection quality in rural areas.
- **Digital Literacy:** The I in all clusters indicates the need for educational programs that address digital skills, especially for vulnerable groups.
- **Subsidies:** The I in Cluster 4 highlights the importance of assessing the economic viability of subsidies to ensure their impact.

4.4.6. Future Research

Future research could expand the panel of experts and use neutrosophic matrices to integrate HJ-Biplot projections with T, I, and F scales, developing a hybrid model that combines quantitative and qualitative analysis. This would strengthen inclusive policymaking to close the digital divide in Latin America and the Caribbean.

5. Conclusions

This study demonstrates that deep digital inequality in Latin America, shaped by socioeconomic and geographic factors, worsens historical gaps in health and education. Through a multivariate HJ-Biplot analysis, complemented by a Neutrosophic Delphi approach, countries were grouped into clusters with varying connectivity levels, highlighting Chile's leadership in contrast to the lagging positions of El Salvador, Paraguay, and the Dominican Republic. The neutrosophic perspective was crucial in revealing indeterminacies in digital access, such as variable connection quality and the psychosocial effects of hyperconnectivity, which demand specific attention in public policy.

The main methodological contribution of this research is the integration of HJ-Biplot analysis with the Neutrosophic Delphi method. While HJ-Biplot effectively visualized the multidimensional complexity of connectivity, the neutrosophic approach allowed for modeling and quantifying the ambiguity inherent in digital inclusion policies. By incorporating indeterminacy (I) alongside truth (T) and falsity (F) in expert opinions, the method evaluates aspects that classical statistics might overlook, such as quality of use, digital skills, and psychosocial risks. This combination offers a more complete diagnosis and a robust framework for designing public policies that account for the region's uncertainty and qualitative complexities.

The findings highlight the urgent need to make connectivity a regional priority, requiring comprehensive public policies that include infrastructure investment, digital literacy programs, and subsidies to reduce socioeconomic and urban-rural inequality. The Neutrosophic Delphi approach confirms that strategies must address not only the presence or absence of access but also ambiguities like mental health impacts. Future research should expand the sample of countries and include new

variables like gender and educational level to inform the creation of inclusive policies and prevent the digital divide from becoming a new form of exclusion.

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